

Effect of α -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles on thermal conductivity of SiO₂ based hybrid nanofluids

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ABSTRACT

During this study, Tetraethyl Orthosilicate { Si(OC₂H₅)₄ }, Ammonium Hydroxide { NH₄OH } and Ethanol { C₂H₆O } were used as raw materials to composed SiO₂ nanoparticles by Sol Gel method. The properties of nanopowder (SiO₂) were studied by X-ray diffraction, Thermogravimetric Analysis and, Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). Hybrid nanofluids of SiO₂ - α -Al₂O₃ were created and their thermal conductivity was studied. Their stability was also gauged by calculating Zeta Potential.

Keywords: SiO₂ nanopowder, Sol Gel method. Hybrid nanofluids

INTRODUCTION

Development of nanosciences has allowed production of nanoparticles from various materials with different types. Nanoparticles feature greater surface to volume ratio and mobility, which gives them special abilities. According to the unique properties of nanoparticles such as electrical and optical, magnetic, mechanical and thermal, they can be used in wide variety of applications including drug delivery, food processing and packing, coatings, adsorption, photo-catalytic and heat transfer fluids. Nanofluids are made by dispersing different nanoparticles, including elementary particles (such as Si, Cu, Al, Ag and Au), metal or non-metal oxides (ZnO, SiO₂, MgO, Al₂O₃, TiO₂, CuO) and organic materials (carbon nanotubes (CNT) and multi walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) and graphene) with nanometer size range, in a base fluid such as alcohol, distilled water, ethylene glycol (EG), engine oil and other conventional fluids [1]. Nanofluids are a new class of fluids engineered by dispersing nanometer-sized materials (nanoparticles, nanofibers, nanotubes, nanowires, nanorods, nanosheet, or droplets) in base fluids. In recent years, nanofluids have attracted more and more attention. The main driving force for nanofluids research lies in a wide range of applications [2]. The nano-materials attain ultra-high and fascinating features like viscosity, thermal conductivity and surface tension in contrast to the base materials. The inclusion of

nanoparticles and base fluids improves the thermal capability of base liquids more precisely. This substantial issue is solved by utilizing the nanoparticles as an energy source with immersion with base fluids [3]. Nanofluids have been used instead of conventional fluids to enhance the heat transfer rate or prevent overheating in heat exchange applications. Numerous investigators reported that conventional cooling fluids, such as water, oil, glycol and ethylene, which are commonly used in heat exchangers have low thermal conductivity compared to metallic and non-metallic nanoparticles [4]. With the prominence of the thermal conductivity advantages of nanofluids, nanofluids are widely used in automotive, electronics, solar energy, etc. Other than applications in conventional fields, nanofluids also have important applications in medicine. In the medical field, it is used to transport drugs and destroy cancer cells. In the process of oil exploitation, the efficiency of oil exploitation can be improved. With wider applications, a number of factors have been found to affect the thermal conductivity of nanofluids, such as particle size and shape, particle concentration, particle aggregation, fluid stability, temperature and magnetic field [5]. Adding a small amount of solid nanoparticles to the base fluid increases the mass transfer coefficient. Some researchers believe that the mainly responsible mechanism in the improvement of mass transfer process, is Brownian motion of suspended nanoparticles which is similar to the heat

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transfer enhancement in nanofluid [6]. Nanofluid stability is the most important requirement to guarantee the conservation of enhanced thermophysical properties. Large surface area to volume ratio can result in aggregation and sedimentation of nanoparticles, which can compromise the target operation. To obtain a stable nanofluid, two methods are generally used: chemical methods and physical methods. The former includes the use of surfactants, surface modification and pH adjustment. The latter, instead, consist of ultrasonic agitation, homogenization and ball milling. To date, there is no standard method to analyze nanofluids stability. Many papers checked stability only through visual inspection, while a smaller number of studies also reported a zeta potential analysis. Zeta potential is defined as the potential difference between the nanoparticles surface and the base fluid stationary layer that is attached to nanoparticles. Nanofluids with high absolute zeta potential are electrically stable, while nanofluids with low absolute zeta potential are unstable [7]. All the steps of production, use and waste disposal of nanoparticles may lead to their release into water, soil and air. So, investigation of their uptake, bio accumulation, bio transformation and the risks posed by nanomaterials is urgently needed. There is also growing need to develop technologies for soil protection and remediation. Phytoremediation techniques, are eco-friendly and less invasive, more cost effective and restorative compared to conventional methods. Aluminum oxide nanoparticles (Al_2O_3 -NPs) are among the most widely used nanosized materials. Aluminum toxicity to

plants is well known, while only a few studies have been conducted to investigate the phytotoxicity of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles [8].

METHODS AND MATERIAL

SiO_2 nanoparticles were produced by using sol-gel method. Analytical grade Tetraethyl Ortho-silicate (TEOS, 99%), absolute ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$, 99.9%), and ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH , 30%) were utilized without further purification.

A certain amount of Ethanol was taken in 20 ml of distilled water. The solution was stirred using a magnetic stirrer at 300 rpm for 10 minutes. Then Tetraethyl Orthosilicate (TEOS) was added drop wise for two hours. Then Ammonium Hydroxide was added until the pH of 11 was achieved and the solution was then stirred for five hours. Post that the solution was centrifuged and subsequently washed with ethanol thrice. Then it was placed in oven at 70°C for 24 hours. The solid thus obtained was then calcinated at 500°C for two hours. Post calcination the solid was crushed to obtain SiO_2 nanopowder. The XRD pattern of SiO_2 was obtained using X-ray diffractometer. TGA Analysis was carried out as well. The surface morphology of particles was measured by Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM: JEOL-2010) with an accelerating voltage of 100kV.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Fig 1 shows XRD pattern of synthesized nano-powder after calcination.

Fig 1 XRD pattern of SiO_2 nanoparticles

This broad XRD reflection peak may be due to the small size and incomplete inner structure of the

prepared particles. This demonstrates that a high percentage of these particles are amorphous [9]. No

other impurity peak is present which represents the purity of the silica nanoparticles. Fig 2 shows TEM images of prepared SiO₂ nanoparticles

Fig 2. TEM images of nanoparticles post calcination.

The above TEM images confirm that the morphology consists of low aggregation of almost spherical nanoparticle. Fig 3 displays the TGA analysis that was carried out of the above mentioned nanoparticles.

Fig 3. TGA Analysis of SiO₂ nanoparticles

There was a weight loss of about 10.85% till the temperature 160°C. Post that rate of weight loss seemed to decrease. Till about 400°C, there was further loss of 3.95%, 1.75% loss till 600°C and a meagre 1.23 % loss till 800°C. SiO₂ displayed excellent thermal stability as about 18.21g of material

was remaining post TGA from the original 21.63g. Fig 4 shows the variation of thermal conductivity of SiO₂ with three different sizes of α- Al₂O₃. All the materials were disbursed in Ethylene Glycol.

SiO2		SiO2 + Al2O3 (1)	
Temperature (Degrees)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Temperature (Degrees)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)
30.9	0.159	30.59	0.227
32.53	0.185	32.99	0.239
36.28	0.227	35.19	0.268
38.81	0.242	37.52	0.29
41.85	0.248	41.78	0.322
44.82	0.259	45.06	0.333
		45.38	0.344

SiO2 + Al2O3 (2)		SiO2 + Al2O3 (3)	
Temperature (Degrees)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Temperature (Degrees)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)
31.99	0.224	30.85	0.259
33.8	0.227	31.96	0.276
35.06	0.233	33.99	0.309
36.81	0.259	35.89	0.349
38.26	0.265	38.77	0.407
39.81	0.277	42.43	0.503
42.23	0.292	48.46	0.490
45.41	0.295		

Fig 4 - Variation of Thermal conductivity with different sizes of α - Al₂O₃ nanoparticles

Upon addition of α - Al₂O₃ to SiO₂ it was observed that the thermal conductivity of SiO₂ nanomaterials increased by at least 40%. Moreover, with change in size of α - Al₂O₃, the thermal conductivity also changed. Fig 5 displays the variation of Zeta Potential of SiO₂ with three different sizes of α - Al₂O₃

Measurement Results

Date : 19 December 2024 15:07:39
 Measurement Type : Zeta Potential
 Sample Name : SiO2
 Temperature of the Holder : 24.9 °C
 Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 16.166 mPa-s
 Conductivity : 0.206 mS/cm
 Electrode Voltage : 3.4 V

Calculation Results

Peak No.	Zeta Potential	Electrophoretic Mobility
1	-25.5 mV	-0.000006 cm ² /Vs
2	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs
3	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs

Zeta Potential (Mean) : -25.5 mV
 Electrophoretic Mobility Mean : -0.000006 cm²/Vs

Measurement Results

Date : 19 December 2024 15:12:16
 Measurement Type : Zeta Potential
 Sample Name : SiO2 1
 Temperature of the Holder : 25.0 °C
 Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 16.099 mPa-s
 Conductivity : 0.206 mS/cm
 Electrode Voltage : 3.4 V

Calculation Results

Peak No.	Zeta Potential	Electrophoretic Mobility
1	-79.9 mV	-0.000018 cm ² /Vs
2	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs
3	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs

Zeta Potential (Mean) : -79.9 mV
 Electrophoretic Mobility Mean : -0.000018 cm²/Vs

Measurement Results

Date : 19 December 2024 15:17:28
 Measurement Type : Zeta Potential
 Sample Name : SiO2 2
 Temperature of the Holder : 24.8 °C
 Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 16.200 mPa-s
 Conductivity : 0.206 mS/cm
 Electrode Voltage : 3.4 V

Calculation Results

Peak No.	Zeta Potential	Electrophoretic Mobility
1	-36.9 mV	-0.000008 cm ² /Vs
2	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs
3	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs

Zeta Potential (Mean) : -36.9 mV
 Electrophoretic Mobility Mean : -0.000008 cm²/Vs

Measurement Results

Date : 19 December 2024 15:22:28
 Measurement Type : Zeta Potential
 Sample Name : SiO2 3
 Temperature of the Holder : 24.9 °C
 Dispersion Medium Viscosity : 16.166 mPa-s
 Conductivity : 0.206 mS/cm
 Electrode Voltage : 3.4 V

Calculation Results

Peak No.	Zeta Potential	Electrophoretic Mobility
1	-26.1 mV	-0.000006 cm ² /Vs
2	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs
3	-- mV	-- cm ² /Vs

Zeta Potential (Mean) : -26.1 mV
 Electrophoretic Mobility Mean : -0.000006 cm²/Vs

Fig shows variation of zeta potential with addition of α - Al₂O₃. SiO₂ 1,2 and 3 depict SiO₂ mixed with the respective 3 sizes of α - Al₂O₃

It can be seen that SiO₂ when disbursed in ethylene glycol is not particularly stable (Zeta Potential - 25.5mV). But upon addition of α - Al₂O₃

nanoparticles, its stability increases as displayed (- 79.9mV, - 36.9mV, - 26.1mV).

CONCLUSIONS

According to the XRD measurements the synthesized nanoparticle was found to be SiO₂. The nanoparticle was amorphous in nature. The TGA analysis showed that (which) nanoparticle was particularly stable in the range 200°C - 400°C. TEM images displayed that the nanoparticles were spherical in nature. Small amount of agglomeration was observed in the images.

Thermal conductivity measurements displayed that there was a significant increase (more than 40% at least) in the thermal conductivity of SiO₂ after prepared hybrid nanofluid with α - Al₂O₃.

Zeta potential values indicated that upon preparing hybrid nanofluids stability of SiO₂ increased which attests to the stability of the hybrid nanofluid.

It can be concluded that preparing hybrid nanofluids with α - Al₂O₃ can drastically affect the properties of SiO₂ and increase its thermal conductivity

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